

THE INFLUENCE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, SELF EFFICACY, AND COMPETENCY ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE WITH JOB SATISFACTION AS MEDIATION VARIABLE (STUDY AT BANK BTN KCS MALANG)

Niken Eka Maharani Elkhori, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia

Corresponding author: ekameniken@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research is to determine the influence of emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, competence, on employee performance with job satisfaction as a mediating variable. This research uses quantitative research using data in the form of numbers and analyzed with SmartPLS 3.0. The research population and sample are employee BTN KCS Poor. The result prove that intelligence emotional influential positive And significant on employee performance, self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on employee performance and competence has a negative and insignificant effect on employee performance, job satisfaction cannot mediate intelligence emotional to performance employee, satisfaction Work No can mediate self efficacy to performance employee, And satisfaction work can mediate competence to employee performance.

Keywords: *Intelligence Emotional, Self Efficacy, Competence, Performance Employee, Satisfaction Work*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the world of banking, Human Resources (HR) has a crucial role for company. Employees are an important element of HR because they are the driving force Which active in operate various activity company. They must capable adapt self with various demands Which originate from company That Alone, need public, as well as development era (Saputra et al., 2023). By Because That, management need manage employees effectively and progressively so that work programs can run smoothly (Putra & Rustono, 2018). Every company definitely wants employees who don't just have performance Good, but Also own pattern think Which Keep going develop. So from That, management must understand the factors that influence employee performance and take appropriate steps step Which required For increase

performance so that objective term long company can achieved (A. Manafe et al., 2023).

Performance refers to the quality and quantity standards that employees must meet when completing their tasks with full responsibility (Eka & Sugiarto, 2022). Results of the work that employees have done and in accordance with their respective duties called with performance employee. Performance employee No can separated with satisfaction Work Which become reject measuring success company. Satisfaction Work happen when employee capable operate task they with productive And moment company can fulfil hope employee. However, if the relationship between superiors and subordinates is not good then, work is not will run smoothly and can cause a decrease in employee job satisfaction. By Therefore, it is important for them to support and motivate each other in order to create positive working relationships and create optimal job satisfaction for all over employees (Harahap & Khair, 2019).

In Indonesia, work with quality Good Still A little with reason facet request because the service sector dominates more and in terms of supply because of the amount of resources people in Indonesia who have the ability to work are still of good quality spelled out minimal (Sopiah, 2023). Wrong One method For repair quality work in Indonesia is by managing and developing employees as human resources superior must have intelligence emotional Which tall. Employee need own the ability to manage their ego and build positive relationships with others, especially with coworkers. This aims to create a full working atmosphere enthusiasm and enable each individual to complete their tasks effectively. Emotional intelligence is a person's ability to motivate themselves, manage emotions, and regulate mood. If emotional intelligence is high, then the mind will be clear and being able to control emotions so as to minimize unwanted things (Ritonga et al., 2022). In fact, a survey conducted by CareerBuilder reported that 71% of recruiters value employees who have emotional intelligence (EQ) more than intellectual quotient (IQ). And 75% of them are also likely to promote employees with EQ Which higher than somebody with IQ higher (Suliana, 2023).

Effective emotional intelligence includes an individual's belief in abilities those who can be an encouragement to achieve goals, or better known as self-efficacy. Self-efficacy influence method individual For feel, think, motivating self, And act (Situmorang, 2023). when a employee have self efficacy Which tall so will show pattern behavior performance Which leads on success. The more Certain that they can carry out their respective duties and responsibilities well, hence performance employees will increase. However, emotional intelligence and self-efficacy sometimes become A combos Which not enough appropriate for employee If No based with ability Work Which based with knowledge, skills, And characteristics in accordance standard employment or can be called competence (Dewi et al., 2023). Competency here means the employee's ability in control his job in a way neat And in accordance with skill each so that it can create good performance (Krishnawati & Bagia, 2021). Included too rich bank, Which where they sued For clever And persistent in accordance with the field each because it is related to customers and the money they are responsible for answer big.

One of the banks that continues to experience growth in Indonesia is BTN bank (Bank Savings Country). Whereas units the sharia Still under BSI, Muallamat, And CIMB Commerce Sharia. With That, BTN Sharia must capable chase started with method improve existing human resources. The object of this research is BTN KCS Malang, via process interview And observation Which done by researcher related with down performance employees, the results showed that sometimes some individuals experienced internal problems such as poor relations between co-workers, lack of self-confidence good, and inadequate skills and knowledge create a feeling of dissatisfaction at work and can hinder their performance. Employees will be able to complete his job with Good And get results Which optimal if influence internal support. Performance employee become factor important Because become reference whether company the can develop or decrease. Performance employee Which decrease can hinder work so you feel less satisfied at work. Based on observations, employees feel inadequate comfortable at work due to their own individual problems that have an impact on its performance.

Thus the aim of this research is to determine the influence of intelligence emotional, self-efficacy, competence, on employee performance with job satisfaction as variable mediation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand one's own feelings and feelings other people, motivating oneself, and managing emotions both within oneself and within interact with person other (Goleman, 2001). Intelligence emotional refer on ability individuals to accept, evaluate, manage, and control their own emotions And person other Which There is in surroundings. Manage emotion involve understanding to circumstances emotions and the ability to relate them to the situation at hand in order to create impact Which positive. Important For remembered that emotion is results from interaction between thinking, change physique, And behavior (Goleman, 2015). Besides That, According to (Salovey & Mayer, 1999) emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to supervise and regulate feelings in oneself and in others, and using these feelings as guidance in thinking and acting. So, the essence of the meaning of emotional intelligence is involve ability For evaluate feeling, Study recognize And value feeling Good in yourself and others and respond accordingly appropriately.

Emotional intelligence in the perspective of the Al-Quran is a person's ability to controlling all his actions in accordance with environmental conditions based on sharia Islam. There is paragraph Al-Qur'an Which state that only people devout Which intelligent his emotions when facing trials in His words in Surah Ali Imran verse 186, which meaning: " You will definitely be tested with your wealth and yourself. And surely you will hear many things were very hurtful from those who were given the Book before you and from people polytheists. If You be patient And God-fearing, so actually Which so That including matters that (should) take priority".

Indicator intelligence emotional according to Goleman (2018): (1) Awareness self; (2) Self-regulation; (3) Motivation; (4) Empathy; and (5) Social skills. Meanwhile

Goleman (2002) states that each individual has their own or more intelligence known as emotional intelligence which was later expanded into five main abilities namely: (1) Recognizing one's emotions; (2) Managing emotions; (3) Motivate yourself; (4) Recognize emotion others; and (5) Building connection.

Self-efficacy is an individual's capacity to plan and carry out actions in order to achieve the desired results. Self-efficacy reflects abilities and beliefs individuals to be successful and have motivation when carrying out their duties. Self efficacy will develop along with improvement ability And experience individual. Process This assist individuals in forming beliefs, thoughts, and behaviors that provide confidence that they capable control environment social they. Self efficacy develops continuously throughout a person's life. The process of developing self-efficacy individuals begin in infancy, continue throughout adulthood and even into old age. Each stage of individual self-efficacy development is influenced by different factors in the environment moment That Bandura (1997). Self efficacy in Islam very recommended, like Which there is on Al-Qur'an letter Al-Ahzab paragraph 21 Which means: "Indeed has There is on (self) The Messenger of Allah is a good role model for you (that is) for those who hope for (mercy) Allah and (the coming of) the Day of Judgment and he mentions Allah a lot" (QS Al-Ahzab: 21). It is written in the word that expecting (roja') mercy from Allah is a moral praiseworthy which can foster a sense of faith and devotion to Allah Ta'ala. What is meant is with roja' is a state of the heart that is completely attached to the hope of achieving it something in the future, where this characteristic shows good prejudice towards Allah SWT. If an individual has implemented the nature of roja', then he is considered to be able to implement self efficacy in Islam.

Self-efficacy indicators according to Lunenburg (2011): (1) Experience of success (Past performance); (2) Experience individual other (Vicarious Experience); (3) Persuasion verbal (Vicarious experience); (4) Empathy; and (5) Physiological conditions (Emotional cues). Whereas factors Which influence self efficacy in individual according to Bandura (1997) is: (1) Culture; (2) Gender; (3) The nature of the task at hand; (4) External intensive; (5) Status or role individuals in the environment; And (6) Information about personal abilities.

According to Wibowo (2019) competency is the ability to carry out tasks or work Which based by knowledge And skills, as well as strengthened by attitude Work Which required in work the. Competence covers character, attitude, behavior, as well as Relatively stable individual abilities when facing various situations in the environment Work. Competence formed from interaction between characters, draft self, motivation internal, And conceptual knowledge. Competence is a key element that a person must have employee For operate his task with efficient. Sutrisno (2015) define competence as skills And knowledge Which strengthened by attitude Work, as well as its implementation in operate task And work in accordance with standard Work Which set. Competence can also be described as a factor that shapes individual traits which has an impact on the results achieved in the work. According to Ash Shawi & Al Muslih (2011) competence in context Islam can called as Ahliyyah, Which refers on a person's worthiness. In syar'i terminology, competence is an individual's

ability to fulfill and carry out the required tasks or in other words, ability individuals who are the basis for fulfilling the rights they must receive or implement responsibilities that must be carried out (obligations). If people really mean it work in accordance with competence, so he will grabbed results from effort it works the. Allah Ta'ala says in QS Al Anfal verse 53 which means: "(Torment) like that This is because Allah will never change a blessing that has been given He bestowed it on a people, until that people changed everything in themselves they Himself, and verily Allah is All-Hearing and the All-Knowing. "

Indicator competence according to Hutapea & Thoha (2008): (1) Knowledge; (2) Skills; And (3) Work attitude.

Performance employee Which quality will produce profit for A company. Performance employees are an effort to achieve legitimate organizational goals in accordance with law And principle ethics company And in accordance with authority And not quite enough answer individual each, Good in matter qualitative nor quantitative (Moeheriono, 2010). According to Wibowo (2007) state that performance employee is A achievement individual on results his job. Which means all the results of the process of achieving tasks that have been completed These individuals can be called employee performance. Employee performance needs to be assessed effectively know whether A results performance employee in accordance with plan Which has made. In Islam, employee performance measurement should be based on justice, responsibility and accountability to produce good and appropriate performance. In the Qur'an discusses performance employee Which Good explained in letter Ash-Shaff paragraph 4 Which It means: "Really Allah loves those who fight in His cause in single file, as it were they a building which is firmly structured. "

Employee performance indicators according to Robbins (2006): (1) Quality of work; (2) Quantity Work; (3) Timeliness; (4) Effectiveness; and (5) Commitment. While the factors that influencing employee performance in a book by Silaen (2021) are: (1) Quantity Work; (2) Quality Work; (3) Knowledge about work; (4) Planning activity; (5) Discipline; and (6) Initiative.

Job satisfaction is individual, which can be had by all individuals however with different levels. Basically every individual will always try to solve it their duties to the maximum to achieve the job satisfaction they desire. Like what Which said Luthans (2006) that satisfaction Work is a circumstances emotion form happiness or sadness arising from evaluation of work or work experience. Meanwhile, according to Robbins & Timothy (2008) job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude towards his work. According to Qardhawi (2004) Muslim employees are obliged to involve Allah in carrying out his work because work is an act of worship. Deep job satisfaction perspective Islam must profitable second split party that is employee And his superior. For example, employee have right on his salary And if superior No hire employee so This includes unjust actions and employees feeling dissatisfied with their work. If Job satisfaction is linked to Islamic law, so it is about sincerity, patience and also taste I'm grateful. Allah will be pleased with his servants who work professionally as described in Al-Qur'an letter At-Taubah paragraph 59 Which It means: "If they truly pleased with what Allah and His Messenger gave them, and

said: Allah is sufficient for us, Allah will give some of His bounty and so (also) His messenger, actually we is people Which hope to Allah (of course Which so That more good for them)".

Indicators of job satisfaction according to Sudaryo et al (2018): (1) Absenteeism; (2) Desire move; (3) Employee performance; (4) Coworkers; and (5) Employee work comfort. Whereas factors influencing job satisfaction proposed by Ghiselli and Brown in As'ad (2000) is: (1) Position/position; (2) Rank/class; (3) Age; (4) Guarantee financial and social Security; And (5) Quality of supervision.

2.1 Framework Conceptual

Based on theories regarding the variables of emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, competence, employee performance and job satisfaction may have direct and indirect positive influences directly on the performance of BTN Syariah KC Malang employees. Thus the formulation The problem can be made into a plot that describes the research framework as follows following:

Information: Influence direct Indirect influence

2.2 Hypothesis

Hypothesis is a conjecture temporary to problem study, until proven through collected data. There are hypotheses that will be put forward in this research is:

1. H1: Emotional intelligence (X1) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y)
2. H2: Self efficacy (X2) influential positive And significant to employee performance (Y) H3: Competence (X3) influential positive And significant to employee performance (Y)
3. H4: Job satisfaction (Z) mediates emotional intelligence (X1) on performance employee (Y)

4. H5: Satisfaction work (Z) mediates self efficacy (X2) on employee performance (Y)
5. H6: Satisfaction Work (Z) mediates competence (X3) to performance employee (Y)

III. METHODOLOGY

This research uses a quantitative approach as a type of research. Whereas The type of research is explanatory research which is used for formulate problems, determine action options, develop hypotheses, recognize variables research, obtain a clear picture of the problem, and determine priorities for further research (Malholtra, 2004 in Supriyanto et al., 2013:7). In study This using the path analysis method (path analysis) because there are mediating/intervening variables between the dependent and independent variables. In this research there are five variables, namely, emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and competency variables as independent variables (X), employee performance variable as dependent variable (Y), and job satisfaction variable as variable mediation/ intervening (Z).

Study This done in PT. Bank Savings Country Tbk, BTN Sharia KC Poor Which located in Jl. Prosecutor Great Suprpto No.87, Rampal Celaket, Klojen, Malang City, Java East. By focusing on human resources, namely employees in the company. Population Which used in study This is employee on BTN KCS Poor. Whereas sample called part of the population (Supriyanto & Ekowati, 2019:20). Sample in this research employee on BTN KCS Malang, numbering 47 employee.

Technique taking sample in study This use technique Probability Sampling, that is, every member of the population has the same opportunity or opportunity to be selected be a sample. Types of Probability Sampling What is used is saturated sampling, which means all members of the population were sampled in the research (Supriyanto et al., 2013:36). In this study the population was 47 people, so the researchers took all of them population As many as 47 people were the sample for this research.

In this research, Partial -based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used Least Square (PLS) for the analysis method, because this research uses five variables so that suitable use method the. Besides That, very practical so that make it easier researchers in testing hypotheses that have been previously formulated. On method This use device llike Which unique computer (software) that is Smart PLS version 3.0.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Results analysis data can be used to test hypothesis this research. With considering the r statistic and the P value, the hypothesis is considered accepted if the P value is less than 0.05. Because this research involves independent, dependent and mediating variables, there are influence direct And No direct. Results testing hypothesis in program SmartPLS can seen using the Bootstrapping Path Coefficient technique which is divided into two, namely influence direct and indirect. Criteria for assessing the significance of direct influence and influence No direct ie score coefficient path

Which shown by mark T-statistic must on 1.96 And probability value (P-Values) < 0.05.

Tabel.1
Testing Influence Direct

	<i>Sample (O)</i>	<i>(O/STDEV)</i>	
H1 Kecerdasan Emosional -> Kinerja Karyawan	0,466	2,420	0.009
H2 <i>Self Efficacy</i> -> Kinerja Karyawan	0,906	10,383	0.000
H3 Kompetensi -> Kinerja Karyawan	-0,504	2,118	0.035

Source: Results by data

Based on data on table on, so can outlined information as following:

1. The Influence of Emotional Intelligence on the Performance of BTN KCS Malang Employees. Influence intelligence emotional to performance employee own score path coefficient as big as 0.466 Which show results positive. Then mark T-statistic amounting to 2.420 > 1.96 with probability values (p-values) of 0.009 < 0.05. It means Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on the performance of BTN employees KCS Malang, then hypothesis 1 is accepted. This indicates good ability employee in manage emotional Which will impact Good on performance they.
2. Influence Self Efficacy to Performance Employee BTN KCS Poor. The influence of self-efficacy (X2) on employee performance (Y) has a path score coefficient as big as 0.906 Which show results positive. Then mark T-statistic amounting to 10.383 > 1.96 with probability values (p-values) of 0.000 < 0.05. It means Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on the performance of BTN KCS employees Poor, so hypothesis 2 accepted. Matter the signifies good ability employee in manage ability And confidence individual For succeed And have motivation when carrying out their duties which will have a good impact on performance them.
3. Influence Competence to Performance BTN employees KCS Poor. The influence of competency (X3) on employee performance (Y) has a path coefficient score of - 0.504 which indicates a negative result. Then the T-statistic value is 2.118 > 1.96 with mark probability (p-values) as big as 0.035 > 0.05. It means competence negative and insignificant effect on the performance of BTN KCS Malang employees, so hypothesis 3 rejected. Matter the signifies not enough good ability employee in carrying out work based on knowledge and skills required.

Tabel.2
Testing influence No Direct

Original Variable	Sample (O)	Q Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
H5 Kecerdasan Emosional -> Kepuasan Kerja -> Kinerja Karyawan	0,132	1,428	0,154
H6 Self Efficacy -> Kepuasan Kerja -> Kinerja Karyawan	0,147	1,350	0,177
H7 Kompetensi ->	0,577	3,327	0,001

Source: Results exercise data

Based on data on table on, so can outlined information as following:

1. Influence Satisfaction Work mediate Emotional Intelligence to Performance Employee. Influence intelligence emotional to employee performance is mediated by satisfaction Work own mark path coefficient as big as 0.132 Which show results positive. Then mark T-statistic as big as $1,428 < 1.96$ with mark probability (p-values) as big as $0.154 > 0.05$. It means No There is influence significant satisfaction Work mediate influence intelligence emotional to performance employee BTN KCS Poor, so hypothesis 4 rejected. Matter the signifies
2. Influence Satisfaction Work mediate Self Efficacy to Performance Employee. The influence of self-efficacy on employee performance is mediated by job satisfaction has a path coefficient value of 0.147 which shows positive results. Then T-statistic value of $1.350 < 1.96$ with probability values (p-values) of $0.177 > 0.05$. This means that there is no significant influence of self-efficacy mediating the influence of intelligence emotional to employee performance BTN KCS Unfortunate, then hypothesis 5 rejected.
3. Influence Satisfaction Work mediate Competence towards Performance Employee. The influence of competency on employee performance is mediated by job satisfaction has a path coefficient value of 0.577 which shows positive results. Then The T-statistic value is $3.327 > 1.96$ with probability values (p-values) of $0.001 < 0.05$. It means There is influence significant self efficacy mediate influence intelligence emotional to performance BTN employees KCS Unfortunate, then hypothesis 6 accepted.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

Leave from results study And discussion previously, so conclusion Which can taken is as following: First, intelligence emotional influential positive And significant to performance employee. Second, self efficacy influential positive And significant to performance employee. Third, competence influential negative And No significant to performance employee. Fourth, satisfaction Work No can mediate intelligence emotional to performance employee. fifth, satisfaction Work No can mediate self efficacy to performance employee.

Sixth, satisfaction Work can mediate competence to performance employee

5.2 Suggestion

Management data in study This use application SmartPLS, Which only allows for partial testing and does not support simultaneous testing. Although some tests show positive and significant effects, there are also negative effects negative And No significant. No significant And own influence Which negative No indicates that the components or variables in this research are not important, but become knowledge new Which Can repaired by party Which concerned nor others. The results of this research can be a motivation for BTN KCS Malang employees to Keep going Study. In study This has prove that satisfaction Work very influence performance employee so that need repaired Again emotional And flavor believe self on self employee.

For researcher furthermore expected can do study more deep with develop and add variables and add other relevant theories outside the variables that have been studied in this research in order to obtain better results and varied. Because study This Still limited on influence intelligence emotional, self efficacy, and competence on employee performance are still mediated by job satisfaction Lots there's a big flaw in it.

REFERENCES

- A. Manafe, H., Yasinto, Y., & H. Djonu, J. (2023). Influence of Emotional Intelligence, Commitment Organizational, OCB (Organizational Citizenship Behavior), And Climate Organization to Performance Employee (One Study Studies Literature Management Source Power Man). *Journal Educational Management And Social Sciences*, 4 (1), 384–397. <https://doi.org/10.38035/jmpis.v4i1.1440>
- As'ad. (2000). *Series Knowledge Source Power Man Psychology Industry* (4th ed.). Liberty.
- Ash Shawi, S., & Al Muslih, A. (2011). *Fiqh Economy Finance Islam*, trans. Ash Omar Bashir. Darul Haq.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *The Exercise of Control*. WH Freeman.
- Goddess, S., Amalia, A., & Huddin, m (2023). *Role Discipline Work, Competence, And Environment Work Physique to Performance Employee*. 17 (4), 2393–2406. <https://doi.org/10.18196/mb.11188.2>
- Eka, S., & Sugiarto, A. (2022). The influence of emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and environment Work to performance employee. *Journal Inspiration Business And Management*, 6 (1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.33603/jibm.v6i1.6781>
- Goleman, D. (2001). *Emotional intelligence to reach the peak of achievement*. Gramedia Library Main.
- Goleman, D. (2018). *Emotional Intelligence*. Jakarta: Gramedia Library Main.
- Please, D. S., & Khair, H. (2019). Influence Leadership And Compensation To Satisfaction Work Through Work motivation Goddess. *Wicaksono & Hermani*, 2 (1), 69–88.
- Hutapea, P., & Thoha, N. (2008). *Competence plus*. Scholastic Main Library.

- Krisnawati, NKD, & Bagia, IW (2021). The Influence of Work Competencies on Performance Employee. *Bisma: Journal of Management*, 7 (1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.23887/bjm.v7i1.28736>
- Lunenburg, F. C. (2011). Self-Efficacy in the Workplace: Implications for Motivation and Performance. *Sam Houston State Universities, International Journal Of Management, Business, and Administration.*, 14 (1).
- Luthans, F. (2006). *Behavior Organization* (10th ed.). Andy.
- Moeheriono. (2010). *Measurement Performance Based Competence*. Ghalia Indonesia.
- Putra, PN, & Rustono, A. (2018). The Influence of Organizational Culture and Work Motivation on Performance Employee Pt Telecommunication Indonesia Region Bandung the Impact of Organizational Culture and Work Motivation on Employee Performance of Pt. Indonesian Telecommunication Region Bandung. *E-Proceeding of Management*, Vol. 5, No (2), 1812–1819.
- Qardhawi, Y. (2004). *System Knowledge Islam* (R. Divine (ed.)).
- Ritonga, BTW, Sihombing, HG, Sudirman, I., Aulia, H., Umri, T., & Safrida, S. (2022). Influence Intelligence Emotional, Intelligence Intellectual And Intelligence Spiritual To Improvement Performance Employee. *Economy, Finance, Investment And Sharia (EQUITY)*, 4 (2), 761–771. <https://doi.org/10.47065/ekuitas.v4i2.2567>
- Robbins, S. P (2006). *Behavior Organization*. PT. Index, Group Scholastic.
- Robbins, S.P., & Timothy, A.J. (2008). *Organizational Behavior* (12th ed.). Salemba Four.
- Salovey, P., & Mayer, J. (1999). *Emotional Intelligence*. PT. Scholastic.
- Saputra, A., Share, I., & Yulianthini2, N. (2023). Influence Satisfaction Work And Loyalty Employee To Performance Employee. *Indonesian Management Journal*, 4 (1), 1–8.
- Silaen, NR (2021). Employee performance. In *Employee Performance*. Widina Bhakti Persada Publisher. Situmorang, I. R. (2023). Influence Self Efficacy And Locus of Controls In Increase Performance Employee In Cassano Café Medan. *businessman*, 12 (1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.24114/niaga.v12i1.43865>
- Sopiah, A. (2023). *News Bad! Work "Quality" in R.I Keep going Down*. CNBC Indonesia. <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/news/20230221064619-4-415482/bad-job-news-self-quality-keeps-falling>
- Sudaryo, Y., Ariwibowo, A., & Sofianti, N. A. (2018). *Management Source Power Man*. Publisher Andy.
- Suliana. (2023). *Not IQ, These are 4 Reasons HRD Prefers Employees with High EQ*. Newspaper Jakarta. <https://koran-jakarta.com/bukan-iq-ini-4-alasan-hrd-besar-oleh-karyawan-dengan-high-eq?page=all>
- Supriyanto, A. S., & Ekowati, V. m (2019). *Research management HR: For thesis, thesis, dissertation, And equipped with examples of journal articles*. Intelligence Media.
- Supriyanto, AS, Maharani, V., & Fathani, AH (2013). *Management Research Methodology Resource Man: Theory, Questionnaire, And Analysis Data* (2nd ed.). UIN Maliki Press.

- Sutrisno, E. (2015). *Organizational culture*. Prenadamedia Group.
- Wibowo. (2007). *Management Performance*. PT. King Grafindo Persada.
- Wibowo. (2019). *Management of Basic Functions to Innovation (1st ed.)*. Rajawali Press.